

Extraction Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) using 2'-Hydroxyacetophenonebenzoylhydrazone

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A light brown 1 : 1 complex of vanadium(V) with 2'-hydroxyacetophenone benzoylhydrazone (HABH) is extracted into chloroform from 0.0–0.5 M CH₃COOH medium containing 0.6–1.1 ml of 0.1% HABH solution. It obeys Beer's law over the concentration range 0.0–3.5 μg V ml⁻¹ having molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity as 8.93 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0057 μg V cm⁻², respectively, at 375 nm. The method has good reproducibility and can be satisfactorily applied for the analysis of steel and reverberatory flue dust samples.

Recently reported hydrazones¹ and many other reagents² utilized for colorimetric determination of vanadium suffer from a large number of interferences and also lack sensitivity. The present investigation reports a simple, rapid and highly selective extractive spectrophotometric method for determination of vanadium using 2'-hydroxyacetophenone benzoylhydrazone (HABH).

Results and Discussion

HABH gives an extractable and stable yellow complex with V^V in neutral to weakly acidic media. In strong acids, fading of the colour is observed, whereas in alkaline medium the colour is not extracted. For achieving optimum and constant absorbance, 0.0–0.5 M acetic acid medium and 0.6–1.1 ml of 0.1% HABH (2.35 × 10⁻⁴ – 4.3 × 10⁻⁴ M HABH) are found sufficient for 20 μg V^V per 10 ml aqueous phase. The reagent prepared in ethanol gives low colour intensity of the complex. On shaking with chloroform (10 ml), equilibrium is attained in 10 s and absorbance remains constant upto 4 min. So 30 s contact time is considered to be reasonable for the system. Vanadium complex is extracted by a large number of water-immiscible organic solvents. The absorbance decreases in the order : carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloromethane, isobutyl methyl ketone, benzene, ethyl methyl ketone, butyl acetate and amyl alcohol. Though carbon tetrachloride gives maximum absorbance, the colour is not stable beyond 15 min. So chloroform is chosen for further studies as it gives a constant absorbance for more than 1 h 45 min. A single extraction with equal volume (10 ml) of the solvent is sufficient to give quantitative extraction and maximum absorbance of the complex.

V^V-HABH complex under optimum conditions of the procedure, shows maximum absorption at 372–379 nm, where the reagent blank has very low absorption. So all measurements were carried out at 375 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.0–3.5 μg V ml⁻¹; the

optimum range as evaluated from Ringbom plot being 0.69–3.32 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity at 375 nm are 8.93 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0057 μg V cm⁻² respectively. The reproducibility of the method is tested by performing eight sets of experiments taking 2 μg V ml⁻¹ each time. The results obtained are highly reproducible with a standard deviation of ±0.0021. The composition of the complex as determined by Job's method of continuous variations is found to be 1 : 1 which is further supported by mole-ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the procedure containing 20 μg V^V, the ions/complexing agents added as their sodium or potassium salts in 10 ml aqueous phase (mg amounts in parentheses) such as phosphate (50); chloride, nitrate, tartrate, acetate, thiourea (20 each); sulphate, thiocyanate (10 each); iodide (8); fluoride (5); bromide, citrate (1 each); 20 volume H₂O₂ (1 ml) and glycerol (1 ml) cause an error of <1%. Ascorbic acid, oxalate and EDTA even in traces interfere seriously. Among the cations, Co^{II} (1.0); Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Hg^{II}, Th^{IV} (0.5 each); Cr^{VI}, U^{VI} (0.4 each); Sb^{III} (0.25); Bi^{III}, As^V (0.2 each); Cu^{II}, Sn^{II}, Ti^{IV}, Zn^{II}, Be^{II} (0.1 each); Pt^{IV} (0.06); Se^{IV}, Al^{III}, Os^{VIII} (0.05 each); Ag^I, Ir^{III}, W^{VI} (0.02 each); Cd^{II}, Au^{III}, Ru^{III}, Re^{VII} (0.01 each) and Mo^{VI} (0.005) have no effect on the absorbance of V^V-HABH complex. Upto 0.2 mg of Fe^{III} and 0.1 mg of Zr^{IV} are masked with 5 mg of fluoride and 20 mg of phosphate respectively, whereas 0.02 mg each of Nb^V and Pd^{II} are masked with 5 mg of tartrate and 10 mg of thiocyanate respectively, when added prior to addition of HABH.

The wide applicability and scope of the proposed method are tested by analysing synthetic mixtures, steel alloy and flue dust samples for vanadium(V) with satisfactory accuracy (Table 1).

Experimental

A Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer with 10 mm

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF VANADIUM(V) IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Composition of sample (mg)	V added (μg)	V found*(μg)	
			Proposed method	Oxine method
1.	Au(0.01), Ir(0.01), Ru(0.005)	5.0	5.0	4.8
2.	Ti(0.05), Cr(0.1), Ni(0.1), Mo(0.001), W(0.01), Fe(0.1), Co(0.1)	10.0	10.2	9.8
3.	Fe(0.05), Co(0.01), Mn(0.01) ^a	5.0	5.0	5.0
4.	Reverberatory flue dust (100)	5.0	5.0	4.9
		10.0	10.1	9.8
5.	High speed steel super rapid extra 500 (50)	1% ^b	0.975%	0.970%

*Average of duplicate analyses. ^aComposition analogous of permendur.

^bCertified value.

matched quartz cells was used. Solutions of V^V and other ions were prepared as reported earlier³. 2'-Hydroxyacetophenone benzoylhydrazone (HABH) (m.p. 164°) was synthesized by the reported method⁴ and dissolved in acetone to give 0.1% (w/v) solution. Acetic acid (4 M) was used. Chloroform (Qualigens 'SQ') was distilled and the fraction distilling at 60–61° was used for extraction.

High speed steel super rapid extra 500 (0.05 g) was decomposed by boiling with minimum amount of aqua regia. Aliquots (1 ml) of the resulting 100 ml solution were subjected to determination of vanadium after adding sodium fluoride (5 mg). Reverberatory flue dust sample (0.1 g) was mixed with a solution of known vanadium content (1 mg) and brought into solution (100 ml) as reported⁵.

Aliquots (0.5 and 1 ml) were taken for determination of vanadium after adding sodium fluoride as above.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution containing vanadium(v) upto 35 μg was mixed with 0.1% HABH (0.8 ml), 4 M acetic acid (1 ml) and deionised water and the volume made up to 10 ml. It was equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 30 s. The yellow coloured solvent phase was filtered and its absorbance was measured at 375 nm against a reagent blank.

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